

A Synthesis of Isocarthamidin

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Naringenin does not undergo Duff's reaction satisfactorily, but by Gattermann's reaction it yields its 8-aldehyde. Subsequent Dakin's oxidation, however, brings about isomeric change, yielding isocarthamidin, identity of which has been established by colour reactions and methylation studies. The simpler 5-hydroxy-7-methoxyflavanone under the same conditions yields an *ortho*-hydroxyaldehyde (6-aldehyde), but when subjected to Dakin's oxidation it suffers the reverse isomeric change and forms the known 5,8-dihydroxy-7-methoxyflavanone.

Nuclear oxidation¹ can be either a one-stage process employing alkaline potassium persulphate or a two-stage process involving formylation and then Dakin's reaction. Although the methods have been extensively employed with other anthoxanthins, some difficulty has been experienced in their application to the flavanones, partly because of their instability in alkaline medium. Alkaline persulphate oxidation of 5-hydroxy-7-methoxy- and 5-hydroxy-7,4'-dimethoxy-flavanones yield the corresponding 5,8-dihydroxyflavanones. These were originally considered to be 5,6-dihydroxyflavanones², but later their structure has been definitely established as 5,8-dihydroxyflavanones³. In the two-stage oxidation, the first step of formylation may be accomplished either by Duff's or by Gattermann's reaction. The former, using hexamine and glacial acetic acid, is not satisfactory in the case of flavanones and forms mainly dark brown amorphous nitrogenous products. The Gattermann reaction, however, proceeds well and affords a good yield of the formyl derivatives.

As a typical naturally occurring flavanone, naringenin (I) has been examined. This furnishes an aldehyde (IIa or IIb) which, when subjected to Dakin's oxidation, yields isocarthamidin (III). This tetrahydroxyflavanone was originally obtained along with carthamidin by hydrolysis of carthamin which is the main glucosidic pigment of the petals of *Carthamus tinctorius* (safflower). Its constitution was suggested to be 5,6,7,4'-tetrahydroxyflavanone (III) by Kuroda⁴, based on colour reactions. Later this compound was prepared by demethylation of synthetic 5,6,7,4'-tetramethoxyflavanone⁵ and 5,7-dimethoxy-6,4'-dihydroxyflavanone⁷, using aluminium chloride in benzene medium. Since this demethylating agent has been found unsatisfactory in the flavanone group, a more satisfactory method of synthesis has been considered necessary. The two-stage method of nuclear oxidation satisfies this need and provides satisfactory yields. The product

1. Seshadri, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1948, 28A, 1; 1949, 30A, 333.
2. Ishwar Dass *et al.*, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1955, 14B, 335.
3. Krishnamurty and Seshadri, *ibid.*, 1959, 15B, 153.
4. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 752.
5. Chopia, *Compt. rend.*, 1958, 247, 1246.
6. Narasimhaচারী *et al.*, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1949, 29A, 404.
7. Zemplén *et al.*, *Acta Chim. Acad. Sci. Hung.*, 1958, 14, 471.

responds to all the reactions and forms acetyl derivative, as recorded by Kuroda⁴ for isocarthamidin. In order to provide a definite proof of its constitution, it has been subjected to methylation, using 4 moles of dimethyl sulphate. The product is found to be 2'-hydroxy-4', 5', 6', 4-tetramethoxychalcone (IV). This method takes a long time to complete; the flavanone ring opens in the course of the reaction and it is susceptible to isomeric change. On the other hand, the use of a large excess of dimethyl sulphate enables the methylation to proceed rapidly without complication⁵ and the product is found to be 5,6,7, 4'-tetramethoxyflavanone. The formation of this methyl ether definitely establishes the constitution of the oxidation product as isocarthamidin.

The point, which has not been definitely established, is the position of the aldehyde group in naringenin aldehyde. Based on the general reactions of flavonoids having hydroxyl groups in the 5- and 7-positions, position 8 (see IIa) could be suggested as the most likely. Then during the oxidation with alkaline hydrogen peroxide, isomeric change should have taken place owing to the opening of the oxygen ring and subsequent ring closure to provide the more favoured 5, 6, 7-orientation of hydroxyl groups.

In exploratory experiments, 5-hydroxy-7-methoxyflavanone (Va) was first used as a convenient and simple member of the group. In this case two products were obtained, viz., a colorless compound (m.p. 134°) and a yellow compound (m.p. 184°). The former responded to a +ve pyrylium salt test for *ortho*-hydroxyaldehyde when condensed with *p*-methoxyacetophenone, using hydrogen chloride in acetic acid. Based on this reaction, it is given the structure of 6-aldehyde (Vb). It undergoes Dakin's oxidation, but the product is found to be 5, 8-dihydroxy-7-methoxyflavanone (VI), obtained also by persulphate oxidation⁶⁻⁸ of 5-hydroxy-7-methoxyflavanone. The easy isomeric change of 5, 6-dihydroxy-7-methoxyflavanone to the 5, 8-dihydroxy isomer has already been proved. The higher melting product (m. p. 184°) did not show the pyrylium salt test and did not undergo Dakin's oxidation; therefore it may be considered to be the 8-aldehyde. But this point has not been confirmed.

A SYNTHESIS OF ISOCARTHAMIDIN

Both the isomeric compounds yielded sparingly soluble 2,4-DNPs very readily at the room temperature. The carbon, hydrogen analyses of these hydrazones correspond to a mono-DNP and these are most probably the aldehyde derivatives. The parent flavanone afforded its DNP only in the hot condition and therefore this ketonic carbonyl does not seem to have been affected in the above mentioned condensations of the aldehydes at the room temperature.

EXPERIMENTAL

5,7,4'-Trihydroxyflavanone-8-aldehyde (II).—A mechanically stirred suspension of naringenin (5 g.) and zinc cyanide (8 g.) in anhydrous ether (100 ml) was saturated with dry HCl at 5-10°. In about 30 min. a heavy, dark red liquid separated. After saturation with HCl for 4 hr., the mixture was left in an ice-chest overnight. The ether was decanted and the oily residue washed free of HCl with dry ether. The aldimine hydrochloride was hydrolysed with water (100 ml) at 80° for 30 min. After cooling, the brown solid was filtered and crystallised first from acetone-light petroleum and then from methanol, yielding colorless small prisms (3.0 g.), m.p. 190-91°. It developed a deep red colour with ethanolic ferric chloride. (Found: C, 63.5; H, 4.5. $C_{16}H_{11}O_6$ requires C, 64.0; H, 4.0%.)

It condensed with *p*-methoxyacetophenone in acetic acid solution when saturated with HCl to form a deep red solution. The 2,4-DNP of the aldehyde (formed readily) melted at 271-73° (decomp.), but that of naringenin (formed slowly) melted at 288-89° (decomp.).

Dakin's Oxidation of Naringenin Aldehyde: 5,6,7,4'-Tetrahydroxyflavanone (Isocarthamidin, III).—A cooled solution (5-10°) of the above aldehyde (1.0 g.) in pyridine (20 ml) and aqueous 5% NaOH solution (4 ml) was treated with hydrogen peroxide (4 ml, 6%) in course of 20 min. The colour changed from reddish brown to greenish brown. After 2 hr., the solution was acidified with HCl (dil.) and extracted repeatedly with ether. On distilling the solvent, a yellow residue was left which was crystallised from ethyl acetate-benzene mixture in yellow rectangular prisms (0.35 g.), m.p. 239-40° (decomp.) (lit.³ m.p. 240°). It showed a deep brown colour with aqueous alkali (2N). Its ethanolic solution developed a bluish green colour with ferric chloride, changing rapidly to reddish brown, and a magenta colour with magnesium and HCl.

On acetylation with acetic anhydride and a trace of H_2SO_4 (conc.) in the cold for 4 hr., it provided acetylisocarthamidin which was crystallised from ethyl acetate-ether in colorless tiny prisms, m.p. 179-80° (lit.³ m.p. 179-80°). Methylation with dimethyl sulphate (4 moles, 16 hr.) and potassium carbonate in acetone medium furnished 2'-hydroxy-4',5',6',4-tetramethoxychalcone which separated as orange-yellow, wedge-shaped crystals

from methanol, m.p. 139-40°, undepressed by an authentic sample². Methylation with excess methyl sulphate (30 moles, 4 hr. reflux) yielded 5,6,7,4'-tetramethoxyflavanone⁵.

5-Hydroxy-7-methoxyflavanone-6-aldehyde.—A stirred suspension of 5-hydroxy-7-methoxyflavanone⁵ (2 g.) and zinc cyanide (5 g.) in anhydrous ether (100 ml) was saturated with dry HCl gas for 4 hr. After 24 hr. the ether was decanted and the aldimine hydrochloride hydrolysed with water as in the earlier case. The solid product was crystallised from acetone-light petroleum; the first fraction (8-aldehyde) was obtained in yellow, elongated rectangular plates (0.6 g.), m.p. 184-86° (decomp.). (Found: C, 68.6; H, 4.9. $C_{17}H_{14}O_5$ requires C, 68.5; H, 4.7%). It showed a red colour with ethanolic ferric chloride. It did not exhibit any marked colour with *p*-methoxyacetophenone and HCl in acetic acid. Its 2,4-DNP melted at 234-36° (decomp.). (Found: C, 57.4; H, 4.2. Calc. for $C_{23}H_{18}O_8N_4$: C, 57.7; H, 3.8%).

The later fraction (6-aldehyde) was crystallised from methanol in colorless, long prismatic needles and rods (0.5 g.), m.p. 134-35°. (Found: C, 68.3; H, 4.3. $C_{17}H_{14}O_5$ requires C, 68.5; H, 4.7%). It developed a red colour with EtOH-FeCl₃ and an orange colour with H₂SO₄ (conc.). It condensed with *p*-methoxyacetophenone in acetic acid solution, when saturated with HCl gas, to form a red solution. The 2,4-DNP melted at 266-68° (decomp.). (Found: C, 56.7; H, 4.3. Calc. for $C_{23}H_{18}O_8N_4$: C, 57.7; H, 3.8%).

Dakin's Oxidation of 5-Hydroxy-7-methoxyflavanone-6-aldehyde: 5,8-Dihydroxy-7-methoxyflavanone (VI).—A solution of the colorless, lower-melting aldehyde (m.p. 134-35°) (0.5 g.) in pyridine (20 ml) and aqueous NaOH (0.5 g. in 30 ml) and hydrogen peroxide (5 ml, 6%) were employed and the product was worked up as in the earlier case. It (0.2 g.) was crystallised from ethyl acetate in pale yellow, tiny prisms, m.p. 248-40° (decomp.). It developed a green colour with EtOH-FeCl₃, changing to brown with excess. Mixed m.p. with an authentic sample³ of 5,8-dihydroxy-7-methoxyflavanone remained undepressed.